

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: CORE River variables

ag - aggregation for the highest-frequency output; i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval (in model); c: cumulative over sampling period

MED domain, Version: 22 sept 2022

output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
rivo	m3 s-1	a	River Discharge	water_flux_to_downstream	x	x				CORE	
mrro	kg m-2 s-1	a	Total Runoff	runoff_flux	x	x				CORE	
areacellr	m2		Grid-Cell Area for River Model Variables	cell_area			fx			CORE	

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 1 River variables

ag - aggregation for the highest-frequency output: i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval (in model); c: cumulative over sampling period

MED domain, Version: 22 sept 2022

output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
mrros	kg m-2 s-1	a	Surface Runoff	surface_runoff_flux	x	x				TIER 1	
										TIER 1	

